

Simultaneous Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium and Osmium with Salicylaldehyde Hydrazone (SH).

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Salicylaldehyde hydrazone (SH) has been recommended as a chromogenic reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) and osmium(VIII) in presence of each other and several other diverse ions. SH forms 1:2 and 1:1 complexes with palladium and osmium respectively. The complexes show maximum absorbance at 425 nm and 430 nm in the pH ranges 3.0 to 5.0 and 9.5 to 10.0 respectively. The colour systems obey Beer's law upto 21 ppm and 19.7 ppm respectively. The sensitivities of the colour reactions are $0.02 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and $0.06 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ for palladium and osmium respectively.

VERY few hydrazones have been used as colorimetric reagents for the detection and determination of metal ions¹⁻³. The analytical applications of hydrazones have been reviewed recently by Katyal and Dutt³. A highly selective and sensitive method for the determination of cobalt and iron with salicylaldehyde hydrazone has already been reported⁴. Survey of literature showed that no more work has been carried out on hydrazones derived from salicylaldehyde and its derivatives. These reagents can act as good chelating agents because hydroxy group and nitrogen atom are suitably located in the molecules. The present paper deals with the spectrophotometric determination of Pd(II) and Os(VIII) in a presence of each other and number of other metal ions with salicylaldehyde hydrazone.

Experimental

Solutions of metal ions were standardised by conventional methods. Absorbance was measured with a unicam SP 600, Spectrophotometer, with 10mm matched glass cells.

Diverse ion solutions were prepared by dissolving the corresponding analytical grade metal chlorides, sulphates or nitrates in doubly distilled water.

Determination of Pd(II) :

To a suitable aliquot of palladium(II) add excess of ligand in acetone. Adjust the pH between 3.0 to 5.0 in a total volume of 10 ml, maintaining 75% (v/v) acetone concentration (to avoid precipitation of ligand). Heat the contents on a steam bath for half an hour, and then raise the volume to 10 ml by adding water of the same pH, followed by 10 ml of freshly distilled chloroform. Shake the contents on a shaking machine and allow to stand for few minutes for equilibration. Measure the absorbance chloroform layer against a ligand blank prepared under identical conditions at 425 nm.

Determination of Osmium(VIII) :

Add excess of the ligand solution in acetone to a suitable aliquot of osmium (VIII) solution. Add requisite amount of acetone and DMF, so as to have 30% (v/v) concentration of acetone and 20% (v/v) concentration of DMF in the final solution. Adjust the apparent pH of the resulting solution between 9.5 to 10.0 and raise the volume to 25 ml by adding water. Heat the contents on a water bath for 15 minutes for full colour development. After cooling raise the volume to 25 ml by the addition of water of the same pH and suitable amount of acetone and DMF, and measure the absorbance against a ligand blank prepared under identical conditions at 430 nm.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves and effect of pH :

The absorbance of Pd(II) and Os(VIII) SH-complexes was found to remain constant at 425 nm and 430 nm in the pH range 3.0 to 5.0 and 9.5 to 10.0 respectively.

Effect of solvent and stability of the colour :

The effect of DMF and acetone was studied by changing the concentration of one and keeping the other constant. The study revealed that a minimum of 20% DMF and 30% acetone was necessary to keep the complex in the solution and ensure the full colour development. For full colour development 20 moles or 10 moles of SH per mole of Pd(II) or Os(VIII) respectively are required.

Palladium(II)-SH and Osmium(VIII)-SH complexes were found to be stable for 24 hours.

Beer's law, sensitivity and molar absorptivity :

The palladium and osmium systems obey Beer's law upto 21.00 ppm and 19.70 ppm respectively. The

optimum concentration range within which the two metals can be accurately determined, obtained from Ringbom plots, are 4.20 to 15.90 ppm and 7.6 to 19.3 ppm respectively. The sensitivities calculated as described by Sandell are $0.02 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and $0.06 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ of palladium and osmium with molar absorptivities 5300 and 3200 respectively.

Composition of complex :

The ratio of metal to ligand in the palladium complex was found to be 1:2 using Job's method of continuous variation, whereas in the case of osmium the ratio is 1:1.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of diverse ions on the complexes formed was studied by preparing solutions containing known amounts of palladium (7.15 ppm) or osmium (15.2 ppm) and different amounts of diverse ions. The following ions did not cause deviation of more than $\pm 3\%$ in absorbance.

Palladium(II) complex :

NO_3^- (9300), tartrate (44.4), citrate (1500), F^- (380), BO_3^{3-} (155), $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (600), Br^- (400), I^- (332), SO_4^{2-} (288), PO_4^{3-} (405), $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (50), Ba^{2+} (60), Sr^{2+} (262), Pb^{2+} (207), Ca^{2+} (75), Cu^{2+} (19), Ni^{2+} (23), Zn^{2+} (13), Cd^{2+} (366), Ti^{4+} (47), Cr^{3+} (86.2), Al^{3+} (105), Os(VIII) (24), UO_2^{2+} (143), Mn^{2+} (109), Ir^{3+} (13). Of the anions tested interference are caused by EDTA, thiocyanate, acetate, thiourea, sulphite and thiosulphate. The presence of cations such as iron(III), vanadium(IV), rhodium(III), platinum(IV), ruthenium(III), molybdenum(VI), bismuth(III), cobalt(II) and gold(III) caused interference in the determination. The interferences due to Cu(II) and Mn(II) are removed by masking them with tartrate.

Osmium(VIII) complex :

PO_4^{3-} (40), F^- (40), BO_3^{3-} (49), $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (40), thiocyanate (14), NO_3^- (200), NO_2^- (200), Br^- (200), SO_4^{2-} (160), thiosulphate (22.5), IO_3^- (80), SO_3^{2-} (38), Ba^{2+} (40), Ca^{2+} (40), Sr^{2+} (35), Mg^{2+} (2), Mn^{2+} (40), Zn^{2+} (20), Pb^{2+} (32), Sn^{2+} (20), Co^{2+} (7), Cu^{2+} (20), Fe^{3+} (6), Pt(IV) (18), UO_2^{2+} (19), Molybdenum(IV) (19) and Ir^{3+} (2). Among the anions which interfere seriously are tartrate, citrate and phthalate. The cations Al^{3+} , Th^{4+} , As^{3+} , Rh^{3+} , Ru^{3+} , Pd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Ce^{3+} interfere. Interference due to Fe^{3+} and Co^{2+} has been avoided by masking them with phosphate and thiocyanate respectively.

The advantage of the use of SH as a spectrophotometric reagent for palladium(II) is in the fact that the metal ion can be determined in presence of large excess of all the other noble metals by extracting the metal complex with chloroform. The interference of osmium in the determination of Pd can be avoided by extraction method.

The method is not so sensitive but the principal advantage of the use of SH is that the determination of Pd(II) can be carried out in the presence of Os(VIII).

Simultaneous determination of palladium and osmium (VIII) :

Palladium forms water insoluble complex at pH 4.0–5.0 which is extractable to non polar organic solvents. On the other hand, osmium forms a complex at pH 9.5 to 10.0. This difference in the extraction characteristic of the complexes has been utilized in the simultaneous determination of palladium and osmium. The following procedure has been adopted for the purpose.

To suitable aliquot containing 106 to 212 μg of palladium and 190 to 492 μg of osmium(VIII), add 2.5 ml of M/50 SH solution. Adjust the pH of the solution in the range 4.0 to 5.0 with hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide maintaining 75% (v/v) acetone concentration. Heat the contents on a steam bath for half an hour and extract the complex immediately into 10 ml of chloroform. Separate the chloroform layer and shake the aqueous phase again with 10 ml of chloroform to ensure complete removal of palladium complex from the aqueous phase. Measure the absorbance of the organic phase against reagent blank at 425 nm and deduce the amount of palladium from calibration curve.

To the aqueous solution, add excess of acetic solution of ligand and 5 ml. of DMF. Raise the pH of the solution between 9.5 to 10.0. Heat the contents on water bath for 15 min in order to evaporate acetone and DMF for full colour development. Raise the volume to 25 ml by addition of DMF (30% and 20% v/v finally), acetone and water of the same pH. Measure the absorbance against reagent blank prepared under identical condition at 430nm and determine the amount of osmium from the standard calibration curve.

TABLE 1—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM & OSMIUM

Pd present in μg .	Pd found in μg .	Os present in μg .	Os found in μg .
42.0	38.0	150.0	140.0
84.0	88.0	190.0	188.2
106.0	104.8	227.5	230.0
170.0	166.7	272.5	276.3
200.0	204.0	380.0	385.0
212.0	215.0	400.0	455.0

The results of the estimation for the various concentrations of the two metal ions used in synthetic mixture are recorded in table 1.

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